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THE RESULTS OF STUDYING THE EFFECT OF VAPING ON THE HUMAN BODY AND ITS PREVALENCE AMONG MEDICAL UNIVERSITY STUDENTS

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Annotation: The students' commitment to vaping was studied and the impact of vaping smoking on human health was assessed. During the investigation, it was found that vaping has no documented benefits, vaping acts as a "nicotine trap" to lure a new generation of drug addicts. The adoption of the strictest laws on the prohibition of smoking is mandatory.

Keywords: vaping, smoking, students, drug addiction

РЕЗУЛЬТАТЫ ИЗУЧЕНИЯ ВЛИЯНИЯ ВЕЙПИНГА НА ОРГАНИЗМ ЧЕЛОВЕКА И ЕГО РАСПРОСТРАНЁННОСТЬ СРЕДИ СТУДЕНТОВ МЕДИЦИНСКОГО УНИВЕРСИЕТА

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Аннотация: Изучена приверженность студентов к вейпингу и оценено влияние курения вейпов на состояние здоровья человека. В процессе исследования установлено, что у вейпинга нет документально подтвержденных преимуществ, вейпинг действует как «никотиновая ловушка», чтобы заманить новое поколение наркоманов. Обязательным является принятие самых строгих законов о запрете курения.

Ключевые слова: вейпинг, курение, студенты, наркомания

Relevance. Young people are increasingly using vaping, a practice that poses a serious threat to public health and is currently an important medical and social problem. After analyzing the number of people who smoke, it will be possible to draw appropriate conclusions: how many people are at risk from exposure to tobacco products, what type of exposure and which organ systems bear the brunt.

Goal. To study students' commitment to vaping and evaluate the impact of vaping smoking on human health.

Materials and methods of research. The analytical method was used in the work. The obtained data were processed statistically. The respondents were students of the medical University aged 18-28.

Results and their discussion. The study was conducted among 274 students, 210 girls and 64 guys among the respondents. According to the survey results, 102 respondents, 37.2 %, smoke on a regular basis, 172

respondents do not smoke, which is 62.8 %. When asked what 20 respondents smoke, they spoke in favor of conventional cigarettes, which is 19.6 %, 53 people spoke for electronic cigarettes, 52 %, the remaining 29 respondents were dual users, 28.4 %. To date, the number of people, including both young people and adults, who use vape, is progressively increasing. Such a high popularity of these devices, first of all, is based on the myth that the aerosol inhaled during smoking is practically harmless, which of course does not correspond to reality. A vape is a battery-powered smoking device that people use to inhale an aerosol produced by a heated liquid. Mandatory elements of any liquid are: water, propylene glycol, glycerin and various flavors [1]. All of these components have a detrimental effect on our body. The consequences of using vapes are not yet fully known. It should be understood that humanity has spent more than one hundred years to come to an understanding of the harm of smoking.

The potential risks of vaping come from several sources: problems associated with a specific device, the composition of vaporized liquid products and the potential toxicity of nicotine when inhaled in concentrated forms. The risk profiles of these inhaled chemical mixtures vary significantly depending on the method by which they are vaporized or heated [2].

The usual solvents for dissolving nicotine were propylene glycol and glycerin, and they are the best studied. To date, there are enough studies demonstrating that propylene glycol causes significant irritation of the respiratory tract during evaporation, which increases the risk of asthma. Glycerin and propylene glycol, getting into the alveoli in the form of aerosols, contribute to the destruction of the surfactant, which increases the extensibility of the lungs and prevents the adhesion of the alveoli. The destruction of the surfactant leads to the collapse of the lung tissue (atelectasis). Experiments were conducted with the inhalation of propylene glycol on animals, as a result, eye irritation and nosebleeds were observed. Propylene glycol is also a stimulating factor for the formation of squamous metaplasia of the larynx [3].

According to the results of experiments on the effect of glycerin on animals, it was revealed that rats have squamous metaplasia of the epithelium lining the base of the epiglottis. The duration of action of the pathogen was 13 days. There are a number of studies proving that both glycerin and propylene glycol have the ability to change the expression of

genes that control the circadian rhythm in the lungs, liver, kidneys, skeletal muscles, as well as another special RB1 gene located on the long arm of chromosome 13 and encoding the RB1 protein of the same name (retinoblastoma protein). All this indicates systemic effects that do not depend on nicotine or flavorings [4].

Exposure to the main component of e-cigarette liquid, propylene glycol, in addition to irritating the respiratory tract (similar to eye irritation), causes airway obstruction and increased shortness of breath in people who have not previously had this condition. It is reported that, depending on the level of exposure, trace elements of nickel, chromium, cadmium, copper and manganese released from the vapors of electronic cigarettes cause or may cause several side effects. These include shortness of breath, cough and wheezing, irritation of the bronchi and lungs, irritation of the mucous membranes of the eyes and upper respiratory tract, impaired lung function, as well as cancer of the lungs, nose and paranasal sinuses of the lungs [5-8].

For example, a case of acute onset of respiratory symptoms associated with severe fixed airway obstruction was reported in a 45-year-old man who quit smoking regular cigarettes and started smoking vapes in large doses 9 months before the incident. His symptoms and severe obstructive pulmonary disease persisted despite smoking cessation and aggressive treatment. Another study reported a series of cases of eight patients who suffered acute lung injury associated with vaping. While most of them recovered with corticosteroid therapy, one died [6].

Intermediate decomposition products by heating propylene glycol and glycerin include formaldehyde and semi-acetals. Formaldehyde is a group 1 carcinogen that increases the risk of cancer during life by 5-15 times. It is present in traditional smoked tobacco in much smaller quantities. Hemiacetals such as acrolein and acetone cause nasal irritation, cardiovascular effects, and damage to the mucous membrane of the lungs, and these byproducts are produced in large quantities using devices with higher voltage [3].

47 respondents prefer electronic cigarettes with nicotine, 57.3 % of the total, 35 were in favor of electronic cigarettes without nicotine only with aromatic additives – 42.7 %. Nicotine is a well-known dangerous chemical that is highly addictive. It can cause an increase in blood pressure, heart rate, blood flow to the heart and narrowing of the arteries (vessels

carrying blood). Nicotine can also help strengthen the walls of the arteries, which, in turn, can lead to a heart attack. Flavorings added to nicotine extracts pose a separate, but no less dangerous health risk. Diacetyl is a food additive that is used in electronic cigarette flavors and resembles the aroma of butter. In the early 2000s, diacetyl was recognized as the cause of bronchiolitis obliterans, causing pneumonia (BOP) in factory workers exposed to it in large quantities [7].

If smoking one regular cigarette is limited in time and, accordingly, the amount of nicotine entering the body, then vapers have unlimited smoking time, as a result of which novice ES smokers often end up in the hospital due to nicotine poisoning.

The first death from the use of ES was registered in the USA in August 2019, and in November 2019, the US Centers for Disease Control and Prevention (CDC), after studying in detail the medical history of those who died due to smoking ES, gave the name of this new disease – EVALI, translated into Russian the name sounds like: "Lung damage related to the use of electronic cigarettes or vaping products." EVALI may reflect a spectrum of painful processes, rather than one specific process. Separate reports of lung diseases associated with vaping describe acute eosinophilic pneumonia, diffuse alveolar hemorrhage, lipoid pneumonia and respiratory bronchiolitis associated with interstitial lung disease.

The CDC is not yet ready to definitively name the cause of EVALI, but presumably it may be vitamin E acetate. Its presence was detected in all fluid samples taken from the lungs of hospitalized patients. Vitamin E acetate can be used as a liquid thickener for vaping [8].

Conclusion. Based on the above, the idea that vaping is a safer, diluted version of smoking is scientific nonsense. They have no documented benefits, but instead act as a "nicotine trap" to lure a new generation of addicts. The adoption of the strictest laws on the prohibition of smoking is mandatory.

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